

RESEARCH ARTICLE

**An ecological study on *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus)
Delile, 1813 meadow in Rachgoun Island
(Algerian west coast, Mediterranean Sea)**

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Abstract

Posidonia oceanica is an endemic species of the Mediterranean Sea, but recently it is actually exposed to anthropogenic pressures by numerous activities of various origins (coastal developments, trawling, anchoring, turbidity, erosion and beach nourishment). The aim of this study is to evaluate the ecological status of *P. oceanica* meadows around Rachgoun Island of Algerian west coast. The entire island is protected according to the Ramsar Convention and a marine protected area in the process of being classified. The ecological study revealed that the density values reveal a dense to sparse meadow, and the cover rates are among similar values on the Algerian coasts, between 70 % and 88.32%. The analysis carried out on structural features shows that these parameters are strongly influenced by multiple factors (depth, hydrodynamics and anthropogenic actions). The biometric parameters and phenological study (length and width of leaves, leaf surface, coefficient A and leaf area index) of *P. oceanica* show that the Rachgoun Island meadows are, globally, in good health status.

Keywords: *Posidonia oceanica*, ecological status, marine protected area, phenological study

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Introduction

Seagrass meadows cover 10% of coastal areas in the world, and characterize coastal ecosystems on more than a third of the coastal strip (>35 to 50 m depth) in the Mediterranean Sea (Hily *et al.* 2010). The surface area covered by *P. oceanica* meadows in the Mediterranean Sea has been the subject of several studies (Pasqualini *et al.* 1998; Giakoumi *et al.* 2013; UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA 2015; Telesca *et al.* 2015). *Posidonia oceanica* meadows play an important role in the ecology of the Mediterranean coast, but are exposed to anthropogenic pressures and invasive species (Meinez and Hesse 1991). These meadows are essential for the ecosystem as they host a diverse range of species and provide crucial benefits. They serve as shelters for numerous organisms, produce oxygen daily while absorbing carbon dioxide, and generate a significant amount of biomass annually (Boudouresque *et al.* 1983). They are valuable hotspots of biodiversity, hosting about 25% of the Mediterranean marine species, which rely on these habitats as spawning, nursery, feeding, and refuge areas (Tursi *et al.* 2022). In Mediterranean, *P. oceanica* develops a underground complex structure able to store large amounts of carbon over thousands of years (Leduc *et al.* 2022). The threats on this ecosystem have highlighted the need to better understand its biology and ecology, in order to better detect the impacts to which it is subject to and how it will be possible to preserve it (Hily *et al.* 2010). This sea grass is highly sensitive to environmental changes, which makes it an excellent indicator of water quality.

Despite their central role in the coastal ecology, *P. oceanica* meadows are undergoing overall deterioration at local scales (Hadj-Aissa *et al.* 2019). Research on *P. oceanica* meadows along the Algerian coast are rare and fragmentary, in general, assessments of the ecological state, without spatio-temporal monitoring, and restoration plans (Tektek *et al.* 2017).

The main objective of this study is to assess the health status of the *P. oceanica* meadows in a protected area classified by the Ramsar Convention in 2005, in seven sites around the island of Rachgoun. The approach adopted makes it possible to assess the state of health of *Posidonia* meadows in spring 2023, through morphometric descriptors such as density, cover and biometric parameters (length, width and surface of leaves), and two index (leaf area index and coefficient A), in accordance with the Integrated Mediterranean Monitoring and Assessment Program Sea and Coast and Associated Assessment Criteria (IMAP), particularly in the Mediterranean Sea (UNEP/MAP-RAC/SPA 2015). Meadows of *P. oceanica* have been designated habitats of priority interest since 1999 (annex II of the Protocol relating to specially protected areas and biological diversity in the Mediterranean of the Barcelona Convention), and finally in the “Habitats-Fauna-Flora” directive of 1992 of the Council of Europe (Directive 92/43/EEC/May 21, 1992, amended by Directive 97/62/EEC).

Materials and methods

Study area

The study sites are located along the coastal area of Rachgoun Island on the Algerian west coast, approximately one mile from the coast in front of the mouth of the Tafna River, on the continental shelf of the Gulf of Ghazaouet (Figure 1). Archipelago Rachgoun presents an exceptional natural heritage preserved with a high level of endemism, the presence of numerous rare or threatened marine species, and vulnerable species on the Mediterranean scale (Allaili and Kerfouf 2015; Tektek *et al.* 2017; Belhadj Tahar *et al.* 2021). Waters of the Atlantic origin bath this coastline. The circulation appears very turbulent along this coast, and favors the dispersion of possible sources of pollution (Milot 1989). The Mediterranean-type climate in this area, hot in summer and humid in winter, with a dry season from mid-June to mid-September, and wet season from October to December (Mehtougui *et al.* 2018). These coastal zones bear numerous resources and opportunities, but they are also exposed to pollution, disturbances and other degradations caused by fishing, tourism and desalination plant (Mehtougui *et al.* 2015; Boukhari Benamara *et al.* 2020; Benallal *et al.* 2020). Two small quays for small fishing and pleasure boats are located on the island. It has been reported that *P. oceanica* was negatively influenced by environmental degradation, increasing salinity and temperature (Fernández-Torquemada and Sánchez-Lizaso 2005).

Figure 1. Sampling area

Sampling

Sampling by means of scuba was carried out randomly in 7 coastal stations in the lower limit of the meadow around the island of Rachgoun. Surface and bottom temperatures and salinity were recorded (Table 1). Two unfrequented control sites are located in the north of the island. The other five sites located in the south of the island, are exposed to regular anthropic activities of small-scale fishermen, swimmers and boaters. The samples were taken in spring 2023, depending on the weather conditions and the state of the sea. Sampling was carried out using a 60 cm x 60 cm quadrat (Boudouresque and Thelin 1985; 1990). Measurement was carried out randomly within the homogeneous meadow (Panayotidis and Giraud 1981). Only areas actually covered by the seagrass were taken into consideration for measuring density. The number of *Posidonia* shoots was counted *in situ* with five replicates, within a quadrat (Boudouresque *et al.* 1990). Meadow cover was estimated as a percentage (%) by direct visual observation. Each orthotropic rhizomes sampled at random in each station was rehydrated and the leaves were separated for laboratory analysis (Giraud 1977a; Boudouresque *et al.* 1983). Samples were preserved in 10% formaldehyde seawater until processing.

Table 1. Geographical coordinates (decimal degrees) and physical characteristics of the studied sites

Sites (S)	Coordinates		Depth (m)	Surface temp. (°C)	Bottom temp. (°C)	Surface salinity (mg/l)	Bottom salinity (mg/l)
	(N)	(E)					
S ₁	35.318436	-1.476922	5 m	21	16	35.4	36.7
S ₂	35.318326	-1.477694	5 m	20	15	35.4	36.7
S ₃	35.318275	-1.477743	5 m	20	15	35.4	36.1
S ₄	35.318532	-1.478311	5 m	22	15	35.4	36.2
S ₅	35.318941	-1.479242	5 m	21	15	35.5	36.2
S ₆	35.324932	-1.481846	10.5 m	21	14	35.4	36.5
S ₇	35.323955	-1.479545	13 m	21	14	35.5	36.4

Data analysis

The health status of *P. oceanica* meadows were assessed according to Pergent *et al.* (1995), by morphometric descriptors measured according to Giraud (1979): density and cover. For each shoot, the biometric parameters (total leaf length, leaf width and leaf area) were measured. Rhizomes were chosen as long as possible without apparent secondary branches (Pergent and Pergent-Martini 1991). The dividing leaf shoots were counted separately (Giraud 1977a; Boudouresque *et al.* 1983).

Two leaf indices were calculated. LAI Index (Leaf Area Index) measures the leaf surface per m² of meadow, and expressed in m²/m². “Coefficient A” was

calculated as the percentage of leaves that have lost their apex (Giraud 1977a). This descriptive parameter provides information for a given site on the rate of grazing by herbivorous animals or hydrodynamics of the site (Wittmann 1981). Maps and graphs were drawn respectively by ArcMap 10.2 software and R studio software version 1.1.456.

Results

General characterization

The average values of meadow density were lowest at station S3 (350 ± 50.39 shoots/m²); while this parameter was the highest at S6 and S7 (781.45 ± 20.5 and 700.10 ± 9.99 shoots/m², respectively). The spatial cover rate of *P. oceanica* revealed fluctuations depending on the study site. The highest cover rate (88.32%) was recorded at S6, and the lowest was observed at S2 with 70%. Regarding the quay very busy with fishing and tourist boats at S2 we can indicate that the coverage follows the same evolution as the density depending on anthropogenic actions. For all other sites the coverage ranged between 73.33 and 82.11 % (Table 2).

Table 2. The coverage and the average values of seagrass density (number of shoots /m²) of the study sites for *Posidonia oceanica* meadows

Sites	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7
Density m²	422 ± 11,20	403 ± 47,44	350 ± 50,39	425,33± 18,74	654,87± 15,4	781,45± 20,5	700,10± 9,99
Cover rate %	79	70	73,33	79	75,50	88,32	82,11

Biometric parameters and phenological characteristics

The maximum value of total leaf length was observed at S2, followed by S6 with 981.30 and 952.20 mm, respectively, while the minimum was also noted at S2 with 178.19 mm (Figure 2A).

Concerning the width of the leaves, it turns out that the maximum was 11.015 mm at station S5 while the minimum value was 9.74 mm recorded at S3 (Figure 2B). The results show correlation between average length and density ($r=0.45953$) and between average width and density ($r=0.5633$).

As for the leaf area, the results obtained reveal that the maximum was 87.59 cm² at S6 and the minimum values were 42.99 cm² and 43.84 cm² at S2 and S4, respectively (Figure 2C).

Coefficient A was the maximum with 100% and 99.45% at S5 and S1, respectively, and the minimum was observed at S6 (72.45%) (Figure 2D).

The results of the leaf area index shows a maximum and minimum of 4.44 m²/m² and 1.10 m²/m², at sites S6 and S3, respectively (Figure 2E).

Figure 2. Average values of leaf length (A), leaf width (B), leaf surface (C), coefficient A (D), leaf area index of the study sites (E), of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows

Figure 3 shows the results of the pairwise Pearson correlation analyses between abiotic parameters and phenological characteristics, summarizing how closely different types of parameters were related. Significant association between Leaf area index and Leaf width with surface water temperature was revealed, with correlation coefficient of $r = 0.7$ and $r = 0.81$, respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Matrix of the results of pairwise Pearson correlation analyses between abiotic parameters and phenological characteristics

Discussion

Posidonia oceanica in all sites presents continuous and horizontal meadows except on S3, which presented low density ($350 \pm 50.39/\text{m}^2$). The density values reveal a dense ($>700/\text{m}^2$) to sparse ($300\text{-}400/\text{m}^2$) meadow, according to the classification of Giraud (1977b). For all the sites, the explored *Posidonia* meadows was considered in "good condition" with an average cover rate between 88.32% and 70% at S6 and S2, respectively (Pergent *et al.* 1995). Generally, *P. oceanica* meadows studied were in good state (Figure 4), and presents a cover rate of more than 70% (Pergent *et al.* 1985; 1989). The leaf area index perfectly reflects the state of health of the seagrass because its estimation depends largely on density. This biometric parameter expresses the combined action of turbidity and hydrodynamics (García-Márquez *et al.* 2024), which allows us to assume that the S2 and S4 sites were the most affected by this hydrodynamic actions and turbidity. Leaf width is a key parameter indicating the degree of turbidity present in the surrounding environment. In turbid environments, *Posidonia* leaves tend to be large, to compensate for the lack of light caused by significant turbidity (PNUE/PAM-CAR/ASP 2016). The increasing occurrence of heat

waves and water turbidity are threats to the existence of seagrass meadows (García-Márquez *et al.* 2022).

Figure 4. Overview of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows at S6 (© M.A. Benallal 2023)

Previous studies conducted in the same area have shown that the shoot density varied from 482 ± 29 shoot / m^2 at the upper limit to 102 ± 7 shoots / m^2 at the lower limit (Hadj-Aïssa *et al.* 2019). Tektek *et al.* (2017) revealed an average density of 520 shoots/ m^2 , which corresponds to a dense meadow. The average values of our study were more or less similar to previous studies. Finally, in the island area, the seagrass meadows appeared to be in good condition as they were in the protected area. In the coast of Algiers, the density was estimated as 114 shoots/ m^2 at Tamenfoust and 172.114 shoots/ m^2 at La Marsa at a depth of 8m (Semroud 1993) and 386 shoots/ m^2 at Anse de Kouali at the depth of 10m (Semroud 1993). In other sites recently studied on the Algerian coast, the meadow of the Gulf of Annaba showed signs of disturbance, considering its weak vitality in particular (Habbeche *et al.* 2022). Our study site presents good vitality of the *P. oceanica* meadows, compared to the central and eastern Algerian coasts.

The ecological status studied in the north of the Mediterranean was 551 shoots/m² at 10 m depth at Plateau des Chèvres (Marseille, France), (Pergent-Martini 1994) and 312 shoots/m² in Ischia (Gulf of Naples, Italy) at the same depth (Rico-Raimondino 1995). On the other hand, much scientific research has been devoted to the study of ecological status, its regression and its restoration in the Mediterranean Sea, particularly on the northern Mediterranean coast. Overall, results indicated signs of distress for several meadows, along the north Croatian coast (Adriatic Sea). Guala *et al.* (2015) show that density ranged from 355±22 to 629±21 shoot/m² at shallow stations (<10 m depth). Despite their protection, its meadows are regressing in northern Mediterranean Sea (Campagne *et al.* 2015). *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, known to be valuable marine ecosystems, have been reported to be in decline as a result of human activities in recent decades. The Algerian Ministry in charge of environmental issues, has implemented the activities related to the "MedKeyHabitats" project in Algeria in collaboration with the SPA/RAC. In the framework of this project, mapping and characterisation of marine habitats of conservation interest were conducted in Rachgoun Island (Hadj-Aissa *et al.* 2019).

Conclusion

The phenological study (length and width of leaves, leaf surface, coefficient A and leaf area index), shows that these parameters are influenced by anthropogenic activities. The analysis carried out on the structural features of *P. oceanica* showed that the meadows are, globally, in good health status around Rachgoun Island, which is a protected site classified by the Ramsar Convention. Comparison of our study to previous ones on the same site shows this habitat has not been suffered any negative impacts. Lack of anchoring practices, application of monitoring activities and appropriate awareness to inform various sea users on how to mitigate impacts on *P. oceanica* meadows have played a crucial role in the conservation of this coastal habitat. These meadows play an important ecological role in the region, supporting very diverse communities. Seagrass meadows are important for coastal ecosystems due to their contribution to enhancing biodiversity, but the maintenance of their integrity has been threatened by several anthropogenic disturbances. In order to initiate protective actions, further scientific research must be elaborated through spatio-temporal monitoring of the state of *Posidonia* meadows, to assess its state of health.

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